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Supporting the Promotion of Equality
in Research and Academia

CEU

CENTRAL
EUROPEAN
UNIVERSITY

GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

2019-2022

GENDER EQUALITY PLAN WORKING GROUP

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INTRODUCTION

Following the results of the assessment on the status of Gender Equality at CEU, the SUPERA team designed the first CEU **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)**, for a period of three academic years. The Gender Equality Plan, together with yearly Gender Equality Workplans provides details on CEU's objectives in 8 gender equality priority areas. The documents define objectives and actions, assigns responsibilities and lists necessary financial and human resources to improve Gender Equality at CEU.

In June 2018, CEU entered a project partnership with four other European higher education institutions, two research funding organizations and a consultancy firm within the framework of the SUPERA project - *Supporting the Promotion of Equality in Research and Academia*. SUPERA received funding from the European Commission for forty months to work towards promoting gender equality in the partnering higher education and research funding organizations, including CEU.

From September 2018 to March 2019, the SUPERA team, with strong support from the leadership and different administrative and academic units, ran a comprehensive assessment on the status of gender equality at CEU. The results of this assessment were published in a report and presented in many fora, including the Academic Forum and the Senate. This report was developed within the framework of the SUPERA project, relying on its external funding, but was very much in line with CEU priorities and written with substantive contribution from a wide range of people from the CEU community. As such, the report can be seen as a self-evaluation rather than an externally driven initiative.

Now it is time for action. The SUPERA team, with the invaluable feedback from the CEU Gender Equality HUB and the Senate Equal Opportunity Committee, has developed CEU's first **Gender Equality Plan**. This three-year GEP is designed to tackle the problems that had been detected by the assessment. They revolve around SUPERA's key priority areas: (1) gender equality in CEU's mission, leadership and access to decision-making, (2) gender equality in

recruitment, retention, and career progression including (3) availability of family-friendly policies, (4) gender dimension in knowledge transfer and research, (5) sexism, gender biases and stereotypes, and (6) sexual harassment. Two more priorities had been added which aim at improving institutional preconditions for addressing gender inequality: (7) gender-sensitive data collection, access and processing, and (8) gender equality institutional structures.

This GEP includes objectives, actions, and a timeline, and should be read together with the *Workplan for the Academic Year 2019/2020*. The Workplan provides in-depth details of the actions to be carried out this academic year. Under each objective, it includes clear indicators of success together with the assignment of responsibilities and the resources needed, both financial and human, to accomplish our goals in the field of Gender Equality.

The spirit of this GEP and Workplan, as of the entire SUPERA project, is to involve members of CEU community in a participatory deliberation process, in order to define our institution's priorities and interventions to tackle gender inequalities, in line with CEU's mission of promoting diversity, equal opportunities and open society.

Andrea Krizsán, Chair of the Senate Equal Opportunity Committee.
Ana Belén Amil, Gender Equality Officer.

KEY PRIORITY AREAS

1 | Gender in leadership and decision making

Women play a role in CEU leadership, nevertheless senior leadership positions (particularly those of the Rector and Provost) have been traditionally male dominated. The composition of the Senate has never been gender balanced. The year 2019 has seen the worst gender composition, with only 21% of elected senate members being women. Although Gender equality is generally supported by the leadership and administration, there is a lack of gender mainstreaming in decision-making processes.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
1.1 Achieve gender balance in CEU leadership	→ Achieve gender balance in the Senate in all constituencies.	X	X	X
	→ Appoint senior leadership ¹ according to their terms with consideration for gender balance.		X	X
	→ Develop and support leadership capacity for women.		X	X
1.2 Mainstream gender in decision-making processes	→ Mainstream gender in all academic and administrative decision-making processes.		X	X

¹ Senior Leadership: President and Rector, Provost, Pro-rectors, COO and Board of Trustees.

2 | Gender in recruitment, retention and career progression

CEU shows a strong vertical segregation along gender lines reflected by a 38% gender pay gap. In the administrative sector, there is a marked gender imbalance (68% are female employees). There is both a lack of transparent, meaningful and clearly communicated ranks, and of pay scales. Therefore, it is not possible to calculate equal pay for equal work. There is also an absence of clear paths for career advancement.

The academic sector is also gender imbalanced, with only 38% female faculty. There is a low proportion of shortlisted female applicants compared to that of men, a low percentage of women in higher ranks, a higher rate of women leaving the institution, and a lack of a university-wide system for measuring and comparing academic staff workload, and making precise calculations on equal pay for equal work/rank at Departmental level.

Among the student body, there is a lower female PhD graduation rate (53%) than that of men (60%).

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
2.1 Improve the situation of the (mostly feminized) administrative sector	→ Create working group with relevant stakeholders' representatives (faculty, high, medium and low rank administration, Trade Union, HRO) to address the multiple problems listed above.	X		
	→ Define transparent, meaningful administrative ranks with correspondent salary scales.	X		
	→ Clearly communicate those to employees in all relevant communication platforms: internal SharePoint website, employee manual, etc.	X	X	X
	→ Develop career progression paths, also within ranks.		X	X
2.2 Promote gender balance in the different academic ranks	→ Identify and put in place measures to improve gender balance across academic ranks.	X	X	X
2.2.1 Make all phases of recruitment gender sensitive.	→ Collect and monitor the gender of applicants for jobs in a digitalized, anonymous manner.		X	X
	→ Improve the gender balance of shortlisted candidates.		X	X
	→ Develop and adopt gender-sensitive recruitment guidelines.	X	X	
	→ Provide training on gender-sensitive recruitment procedures.		X	X

2.2.2 Make promotion procedures gender-sensitive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Diagnose obstacles to promotion of female faculty. → Make promotion criteria gender sensitive. → Chanel IAAR based workload information in promotion processes → Improve transparency of promotion procedures. → Factor care duties into promotion procedures. 	X	X	
2.2.3 Improve retention of female faculty	→ Further diagnosis on sex-disaggregated faculty turnover.		X	
2.3 Ensure equal pay for equal work	→ Adapt IAARs to measure faculty workload.	X		
	→ Make ranks and related salary scales transparent.	X		
	→ Introduce salary bands within ranks.		X	
	→ Calculate equal pay within administrative and academic units		X	X
2.4 Achieve equal rates of MA and PhD completion for all genders	→ Further diagnosis on sex-disaggregated rates of MA and PhD completion, drop-out rates and length of time required for graduation.		X	

3 | Reconciliation of work and study with care duties

CEU's family-friendly policies are perceived by many as inefficient in that they do not constitute an adequate net of safety for those with care duties. CEU's commitment to support reconciliation of professional life and care responsibilities is still not communicated clearly and consistently. Accommodation of care-related issues is often left to informal arrangements and departmental good will rather than being included in policies. Different support schemes developed for students and often used to accommodate care-related issues are general schemes, not tailored to the special needs of students on maternity or parental leave, and thus sometimes prove to be inadequate for this purpose. A need to better communicate, formalize and target is the main concern in the area of care.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
3.1 Recognize and accommodate employees with care-related responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Include short-term childcare space on-campus in the planning of CEU Vienna new facilities. → Develop comprehensive care policy for employees: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Develop guidelines for accommodating flexible and distance work both for academic and administrative staff with care responsibilities. → Review, align with the Austrian context and make more equitable the available scheme supporting employees with childcare duties. 		X	X
3.2 Recognize and accommodate students with care-related responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Review the Family Support Scheme available for students, specially its link to the availability of a stipend. Consider different applicability between female and male students (specifically in relation to birth and childcare in early months). → Introduce a specific leave for care scheme for PhD students within the wider leave of absence (stop the clock) scheme. → Introduce common guidelines for flexible study-plans for students. → Review supplementary financial support (for research and travel) in light of actual need of students with care responsibilities. 		X	X
3.3 Improve communication of CEU's commitment to be family-friendly work and study place.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Make CEU's commitment more explicit in on-boarding materials. → Make CEU's commitment more explicit in recruitment processes. → Review website information on available forms of support (for employees and for students). 		X	X

3.4 Promote a more gender equal distribution of care roles within the CEU community	<ul style="list-style-type: none">→ Launch a comprehensive awareness-raising campaign about care work and gender inequality.→ Devise policies that encourage male members of the CEU community to take parental leave.		X	X
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4 | Gender dimension in curricula and research

There is a relatively strong presence of gender in curricula, partly related to the Gender Studies Department and their contributions, partly done in each department and in interdisciplinary courses. At the same time, the variation among departments is remarkable, which is not necessarily justified by the respective disciplines. On average, 28% of courses at CEU have at least one gender component. This suggests that a great pool of students might never encounter a gender topic while studying at CEU. Given the CEU mission and the future career path of our graduates, this should be considered for future development. There are no CEU formal policies or guidelines on integrating a gender component in syllabi or research.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
4.1 Improve the presence of gender components in curricula and research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Organize deliberative sessions about the place of a gender dimension within CEU curricula and research projects, at a disciplinary level. → Make available and endorse internationally recognized guidelines for improving gender diversity in curricula and research projects, across different disciplines. → Work with volunteer departments/faculty members to improve gender dimension in curricula and research. 		X	X

5 | Gender biases and stereotypes

CEU academic events are not gender balanced. Female participation as speakers is lower than that of men in Departmental events (37% in 2017-2018) and in events from the Rector, Pro-Rector and Provost Offices (34% from 2015 to 2018). Results of the survey show room for improvement in gender-sensitive pedagogical practices: 49% of respondents signalled that male classmates dominate the discussion, 28% stated that professors interact more with male students and 27%, that professors are not using gender-inclusive language. There has been a lack of communication campaigns targeting gender equality in academia. In spite of recent efforts, there is a low awareness at the CEU community about equal opportunity-related policies: 23% of respondents have not heard about them and 47% is only aware of its existence but does not know the content.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
5.1 Improve gender balance in academic events.	→ Revise and clarify the scope and enforcement of the Gender Equity in Events Policy. → Open a complaint channel. → Design and implement a communication campaign on the topic.	X	X	X
	→ Monitor gender balance in academic events yearly.		X	X
5.2 Make classroom interaction and supervision practices more gender sensitive.	→ Provide guidelines for Faculty and PhD students on how to integrate gender sensitivity in their pedagogical practices, with special emphasis on affirming and supporting gender non-conforming/non-binary identities. → Develop capacity on how to promote gender sensitivity in teaching and supervision.		X	X
5.3 Make course evaluations more gender sensitive.	→ Monitor classroom environment by making gender sensitivity part of course evaluations. → Introduce changes in course evaluations to avoid gender biases.		X	
5.4 Raise awareness about the importance of gender in higher education.	→ Design and implement campaigns on the topic (video, posters, photos, prizes) in coordination with COMMS office.		X	X
5.5 Make facilities on campus gender inclusive	→ Make gender inclusive (unisex) restrooms available on each floor of both campuses.	X	X	X

<p>5.4 Increase awareness of equal opportunity-related policies in the CEU community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Coordinate efforts with HRO, COMMS and DoS to provide information to employees and students. → Coordinate efforts with HRO and DoS to make gender equality part of on-boarding process and materials. → Incorporate a quiz on CEU's policies as mandatory requirement for enrolment of incoming students. → Maintain regularly the EOC website and the SUPERA intranet site. 	X	X	X
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6 | Sexual harassment

CEU does have a reasonably good policy addressing harassment cases. However, the procedures of reporting are inefficient and relatively unknown within the community. Also, the absence of trainings on the topic prevent victims from coming forward with their complaints. In the community-wide survey we conducted within the project, the number of reported incidents of sexual harassment reaches 245. These include cases characterized by various degrees of severity, ranging from repeated invasion of personal space to sexual assault or rape. At the same time, the number of formal complaints, as reported in the survey, reaches only 7. This points to a serious problem of underreporting. Fear of retaliation and mistrust in the institutional response were common reasons given by respondents for not reporting these cases.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
6.1 Devise a more efficient complaint mechanism	→ Develop a new institutional system with an additional informal complaint procedure to complement the formal one in place.	X		
	→ Set up a centralized digital recording system for both formal and informal complaints.	X		
	→ Define guidelines for monitoring of number and severity of complaints, and responsibility for statistical analysis and feedback into the procedure.	X		
	→ Provide specific training on sexual harassment to the people receiving complaints and to CEU counsellors.		X	X
	→ Regularize yearly monitoring.		X	X
6.2 Raise awareness about sexual harassment	→ Provide by-stander training to the entire community.			
	→ Incorporate info-sessions on CEU Harassment policy in all on-boarding processes (students and employees).		X	X
	→ Incorporate information on harassment in head of unit trainings.		X	X
	→ Run communication campaigns on sexual harassment.		X	X

7 | Gender-sensitive data collection, access and processing

At CEU, there are important gaps in gender-sensitive data collection that would allow for recurring institutional analysis, especially at the HR level. Overly cautious interpretations of GDPR² constitute another obstacle that blocks data collection and processing by experts.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
7.1 Improve gender-sensitive data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Develop a handbook with specifications of the gender-sensitive data to be collected. → Improve the quality of the current collected data. → Fill gaps in current data collection. 	X	X	X
7.2 Improve access to institutional data for research purposes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Develop a clearance system for accessing and processing personal data that complies with GDPR and allows for high-quality institutional research. 	X		
7.3 Improve gender-sensitive data monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Develop a handbook with indicators to be monitored, frequency of monitoring, and responsibilities assigned. 	X		
7.4 Make data-management systems gender inclusive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Accommodate CEU's data-management systems to allow trans/non-binary/gender non-conforming students and employees to choose their preferred gender markers and names (i.e., in their campus IDs, email address, registration forms, etc.) 		X	X

² EU General Data Protection Regulation.

8 | Gender Equality institutional structures

Overall, gender equality is part of CEU's mission in implicit ways through the idea of open society, diversity, tolerance or equal opportunities, but not explicitly. Institutional data is not analysed systematically from a gender perspective, and there is no strategic planning concerning the promotion of gender equality.

Objective	Actions	Timeline		
		AY 19/20	AY 20/21	AY 21/22
8.1 Consolidate institutional structures for Gender Equality.	→ Make the position of Gender Equality Officer at CEU permanent and internally funded.		X	
	→ Increase capacity for gender equality work within HRO by clearly assigning responsibility for gender equality matters and by training.		X	X
8.2 Make Gender Equality an explicit part of CEU's mission	→ Discuss the place of gender equality in CEU's mission for 2025.	X	X	X
8.3 Establish regular monitoring and planning	→ Produce Gender Equality reports every three years.			X
	→ Design and implement Gender Equality Plans every three years.			X
	→ Produce a Gender Pay Gap report yearly.		X	X

